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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE MAIN ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL LITERACY IN HIGHER PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article examines the fundamental principles of digital literacy in higher pedagogical education, highlights its growing importance within an innovative approach to the education system, and outlines possible approaches to developing digital literacy.

Key words: digital literacy, digital tools, digital principles, digital knowledge, digital technologies.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada oliy pedagogik ta'limda raqamli savodxonlikning asosiy tamoyillari, ta'lim tizimiga innovatsion yondashuv sharoitida uning tobora ortib borayotgan ahamiyati hamda raqamli savodxonlikni rivojlantirishning samarali yondashuvlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli savodxonlik, raqamli vositalar, raqamli tamoyillar, raqamli bilim, raqamli texnologiyalar.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются основные принципы цифровой грамотности в высшем педагогическом образовании, раскрывается её возрастающее значение в условиях инновационного подхода к системе образования, а также представлены возможные подходы к развитию цифровой грамотности.

Ключевые слова: цифровая грамотность, цифровые инструменты, цифровые принципы, цифровые знания, цифровые технологии.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of rapid technological advancement and the global digital transformation of education, the development of digital literacy has become one of the key priorities in higher pedagogical education. Modern teachers are expected not only to possess subject-specific knowledge but also to effectively integrate digital tools and technologies into the teaching and learning process. This shift highlights the necessity of preparing future educators who are competent in digital environments and capable of adapting to continuously evolving technological changes.

Digital literacy encompasses a wide range of skills, including the ability to access, evaluate, create, and communicate information using digital technologies. In higher pedagogical institutions, fostering these competencies is essential for ensuring the quality and relevance of teacher education. Moreover, digital literacy contributes to enhancing critical thinking, creativity, and collaborative learning among future teachers. Despite its importance, the process of developing digital literacy in higher education faces several challenges, such as insufficient technological infrastructure, a lack of methodological support, and varying levels of digital competence among students and educators. Therefore, it is crucial to identify the main aspects that influence the effective development of digital literacy in pedagogical education. The aim of this study is to analyze the key aspects of digital literacy development in higher pedagogical education and to determine the factors that contribute to its successful implementation in the training of future teachers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of digital literacy has evolved significantly in response to the rapid development of information and communication technologies. Gilster 1997 was among the first scholars to define digital literacy as the ability to understand and use information in multiple formats from a wide range of digital sources. Later, Leu, Kinzer, Coiro, and Cammack 2004 expanded this idea by introducing the theory of new literacies, emphasizing that digital literacy is not static but continuously changing with emerging technologies. Their work highlights

the importance of skills such as online reading, information evaluation, and digital communication as essential components of modern literacy.

Further research has focused on the role of digital literacy in educational contexts, particularly in teacher training. Ilomäki 2008 examined the impact of ICT on schools and emphasized that teachers must possess not only technical skills but also pedagogical competencies to effectively integrate digital technologies into the learning process. Seale 2009 also argued that digital literacy should be viewed as a transformative element in education, requiring a rethinking of traditional teaching approaches. These studies underline the necessity of preparing educators who can adapt to digital environments and facilitate meaningful learning experiences.

Recent studies have explored the relationship between digital literacy and critical thinking, as well as global frameworks for its development. UNESCO 2018 proposed a comprehensive framework outlining key digital competencies necessary for lifelong learning and professional development. Raj and Singh 2026 further demonstrated that digital literacy is closely linked to students' ability to critically analyze and evaluate information in digital environments. These findings confirm that digital literacy is a multifaceted construct that combines technical, cognitive, and pedagogical dimensions, making it a crucial component of higher pedagogical education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative and analytical research design aimed at identifying and systematizing the main aspects of digital literacy development in higher pedagogical education. The research is based on a comprehensive review of scientific literature, policy documents, and contemporary educational practices related to digital competence and teacher training. The methods used in this study include:

1. Literature analysis to examine theoretical approaches to digital literacy and pedagogical integration;
2. Comparative analysis to identify common patterns and differences in digital literacy frameworks;
3. Systematization and classification to define and structure the key principles of digital literacy development;
4. Descriptive method to interpret and explain the identified aspects in the context of higher pedagogical education.

The research does not rely on empirical data collection but instead focuses on conceptual analysis and synthesis of existing knowledge to provide a structured understanding of the topic.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The development of digital literacy in higher pedagogical education is guided by several key principles:

1. **Integrativity** – digital literacy should be integrated across all disciplines and pedagogical practices rather than taught as an isolated skill. The principle of integrativity implies that digital literacy should not be treated as a separate or isolated subject but must be embedded across all academic disciplines and pedagogical activities. Digital tools and technologies should be organically incorporated into subject teaching, pedagogical practice, research activities, and assessment processes. Additionally, with the integration of new ICT tools, many universities around the globe have successfully brought positive changes in the organisation of classrooms, becoming a new force and, to some extent, prime assets that have enabled higher education institutions to achieve their goals (Sharma & Reddy, 2015). This approach enables students to perceive digital technologies as natural instruments of professional activity rather than as auxiliary or optional skills. Integrativity also promotes interdisciplinary connections, allowing future teachers to apply digital tools in diverse educational contexts, thus strengthening the coherence between content knowledge, pedagogy, and technology.
2. **Continuity** – digital literacy development must be ongoing, supporting lifelong learning and professional growth. The principle of continuity emphasizes that digital literacy development is a long-term, ongoing process that extends beyond formal higher education. In our research, “The development of digital literacy among students of pedagogical universities,” we observed that students started their university careers with the literacies of paper, pencil, and book technologies but finished having encountered the literacies demanded by a wide variety of information and communication technologies (ICTs): weblogs (blogs), word processors, video editors, World Wide Web browsers, web editors, e-mail, spreadsheets, presentation software, instant messaging, plug-ins for web resources, listservs, bulletin boards, avatars, virtual worlds, and many others. These students did not initially envision a new literacy at the end of their studies. Given the increasingly rapid pace of change in the technologies of literacy, such as digital literacy, it is likely that

students who begin university this year will experience even more profound changes during their own literacy journeys. Moreover, this situation will be repeated as new generations of students encounter yet unimagined ICTs as they move through education and develop currently unforeseen new literacies. In pedagogical training, this principle ensures the gradual and progressive formation of digital competencies—from basic operational skills to advanced pedagogical and reflective use of digital technologies. The learning environment must support multiple perspectives of reality, knowledge construction, and lifelong learning. For this, Ilomäki (2008) states that “teacher technology” skills are important, whereby a facilitator should be able to use the necessary digital skills to scaffold learners in open learning environments. The teacher’s role in education, as described by Ilomäki (2008), shifts from a creator or advisor of knowledge to a learning coach. Continuity supports the idea of lifelong learning, preparing future teachers to continuously update their digital knowledge and skills in response to technological advancements and evolving educational standards.

- Criticality** – students should be trained to critically evaluate digital information, media sources, and technologies. The principle of criticality focuses on developing students’ ability to critically analyze, evaluate, and interpret digital information and technologies. In the context of pedagogical education, this includes assessing the reliability of digital sources, recognizing misinformation, understanding algorithmic influence, and evaluating the pedagogical effectiveness of digital tools. This principle ensures that future teachers become reflective and informed users of digital technologies, capable of making pedagogically justified decisions rather than adopting technologies uncritically. As research by Smitamayee Raj and Ajay Kumar Singh (2026) shows, having mental models to locate, comprehend, and consume digital content makes navigating the web easier for users. Effective use of the web involves strategically searching for information and evaluating its accuracy and relevance(Figure 1).

Figure 1: Core Components of Digital Literacy: A Model of Locating, Creating, and Communicating Digital Content through Critical Evaluation

- Practice-orientation** – digital competencies should be formed through practical tasks, real educational scenarios, and teaching simulations. The practice-orientation principle stresses that digital literacy is most effectively developed through hands-on experience and real pedagogical situations. Digital competencies should be formed through practical tasks such as lesson design using digital tools, virtual teaching simulations, digital assessment development, and participation in online collaborative projects. This principle bridges the gap between theory and practice, enabling students to transform digital knowledge into professional pedagogical action and to gain confidence in using digital technologies in real classroom environments.
- Ethical responsibility** – digital literacy must include norms of digital ethics, academic honesty, and safe online behavior. The principle of ethical responsibility highlights the moral and legal dimensions of digital literacy. It requires the formation of responsible attitudes toward digital ethics, academic integrity, data protection, and online safety. Future teachers must understand issues related to copyright, plagiarism, personal data security, cyberbullying, and respectful online communication. This principle ensures that digital literacy contributes to the development of digital citizenship, enabling teachers to model ethical digital behavior and foster a safe and respectful digital learning environment.

6. **Pedagogical relevance** – digital tools and skills should be aligned with educational goals and teaching methodologies, not used for technology's sake. The principle of pedagogical relevance asserts that digital technologies must serve educational objectives, not replace pedagogical reasoning. Digital tools should be selected and applied based on their alignment with learning outcomes, teaching methods, and student needs. This principle prevents the superficial or decorative use of technology and promotes its methodologically justified integration into teaching and learning processes. For future teachers, this principle reinforces the priority of pedagogy over technology.
7. **Adaptability** – future teachers must be prepared to adapt to rapidly changing digital technologies and educational innovations. The principle of adaptability reflects the dynamic and rapidly evolving nature of digital technologies. Higher pedagogical education must prepare students to be flexible, innovative, and open to change, enabling them to adapt to new digital tools, platforms, and educational innovations. This principle fosters problem-solving skills, creativity, and resilience, equipping future teachers to function effectively in uncertain and technologically changing educational environments.

The identified principles demonstrate that digital literacy in higher pedagogical education is a multidimensional and dynamic construct. The principle of integrativity highlights the necessity of embedding digital competencies into all aspects of teacher training, ensuring that technology becomes a natural component of pedagogical practice rather than an additional skill. Continuity and adaptability reflect the evolving nature of the digital world, emphasizing that digital literacy cannot be achieved through one-time instruction but requires continuous development. These principles align with the concept of lifelong learning and the need for teachers to remain professionally relevant in rapidly changing educational contexts.

The principles of criticality and ethical responsibility underline the importance of not only technical proficiency but also responsible and reflective use of digital technologies. In the era of information overload and misinformation, these competencies are essential for preparing teachers who can guide students in navigating digital environments safely and effectively. Furthermore, practice-orientation and pedagogical relevance ensure that digital literacy is closely connected to real teaching practice. Without practical application and methodological justification, digital tools risk being used superficially, reducing their educational value.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The development of digital literacy in higher pedagogical education represents a fundamental component of preparing future teachers for the demands of the modern educational environment. The study has shown that digital literacy is not limited to technical skills but encompasses a complex of cognitive, pedagogical, and ethical competencies. The identified principles—integrativity, continuity, criticality, practice-orientation, ethical responsibility, pedagogical relevance, and adaptability—form a holistic framework that ensures the effective formation of digital competencies in future educators. These principles highlight the importance of embedding digital technologies meaningfully into the teaching and learning process, promoting not only functional use but also critical and responsible engagement. Moreover, the findings emphasize that successful digital literacy development requires a systematic and continuous approach, supported by appropriate institutional conditions, teacher training, and access to digital resources. Without such support, the integration of digital technologies may remain superficial and ineffective.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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